

Metallic Uranium in Organic Synthesis. Part I.

BY JAGARAJ BEHARI LAL AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT.

In continuation of the work on the synthetic use of metals published from these laboratories (Ray and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 103; Chakrabarti and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 517; Lal and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 565) we have now studied uranium from this point of view for the first time, since this metal is now commercially available. The investigation also has a special interest in view of the fact that like the metal thorium which was very successfully used by Gairdner and Dutt (*Allahabad University Studies*, 1934, 10, 297) in organic synthesis, uranium is also a radioactive element, and as such, is expected to possess high reactivity towards organic reagents.

Uranium has not given very encouraging results in Ullmann's reaction but has proved highly satisfactory in Friedel-Craft's, Reformatsky's and Zincke's reactions. The action of benzyl chloride on benzene, anisol and phenetol in presence of uranium has been successfully tried and the products isolated in good yields. Attempts have been made to study the higher products formed in these reactions, for instance in the case of benzene and benzyl chloride, besides pure diphenylmethane isolated in 40% yield, *symtri*-phenylethane, *o*- and *p*-dibenzylbenzenes and a trace of a sulphur-yellow hydrocarbon, m. p. 71°, have also been isolated.

Uranium, however, is distinctly more basic than any other member of the 6th group of the Periodic Table. Metallic chromium (*loc. cit.*), molybdenum and tungsten (work in course of publication) have all been tried in organic syntheses in our laboratory. The successful results with chromium have all been obtained with organic chlorine compounds in which the chlorine atoms are rather loosely attached to the molecule and are very reactive. All the three metals cannot be used in either Reformatsky's or Grignard's reaction evidently on account of their much less basic character. In Ullmann's reaction, requiring increased electropositive nature on the part of the metal used for the removal of the halogen atoms, chromium, molybdenum and tungsten all fail, while uranium is very feebly reactive.

Details of the successful experiments are given in the experimental part, while those of the unsuccessful attempts are omitted.

Unsuccessful attempts.

Types of reaction.	Reactants.	Expected product.
Ullmann's	Carbon tetrachloride	Hexachlorethane
Friedel-Craft's	Chloroform and benzene Carbon tetrachloride and benzene	Triphenylmethane Triphenyl chloromethane
Grignard's	Iodobenzene and aniline Uranium and bromobenzene	Diphenylamine Uranium phenylbromide

EXPERIMENTAL.

Friedel and Craft's Reaction with Uranium Powder.

Diphenyl from benzene and bromobenzene.—Benzene (12 g.), bromobenzene (8.59 g.) and uranium dust (4 g.) were refluxed for 18 hours when a very feeble reaction took place. The yield of diphenyl isolated on fractionation was only 0.19 g., m.p. 68°.

Diphenyl from chlorobenzene and benzene.—The reaction was carried on as above. The yield of diphenyl from uranium (4 g.), chlorobenzene (12 g.) and benzene (18 g.) was only 2 g.

Diphenyl from iodobenzene and benzene.—The reaction was carried on as above. The yield of diphenyl from iodobenzene (12 g.), benzene (18 g.) and uranium (4 g.) was only 0.25 g.

Triphenylmethane from benzalchloride and benzene.—Benzene (30 g.), benzalchloride (12 g.) and uranium dust (4 g.) were refluxed together on a water-bath for 8 hours. The dark violet product was filtered from the metal and fractionated to remove benzene and unchanged benzalchloride. The solid residue left in the flask crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 92°, and was identified as triphenylmethane, yield 0.9 g.

Triphenylchloromethane and dichlorodiphenylmethane from benzotrichloride and benzene.—Benzotrichloride (15 g.), benzene (50 g.) and uranium dust (3 g.) were heated in an oil-bath at 115°-128° when after half an hour's heating a fairly vigorous reaction took place. After heating for 8 hours to complete the reaction, the deep pink mixture was filtered, benzene removed by heating on the water-bath and then fractionated at 35 mm. and the fraction boiling at 198°-203° and redistilled at 200°-202° was identified as dichlorodiphenylmethane (yield 4.2 g.) and the residue in the flask was crystallised from carbon disulphide and melted at 110°-115° and was identified as triphenylchloromethane, yield 1.2 g.

Acetophenone from acetyl chloride and benzene.—Benzene (18 g.), acetyl chloride (12 g.) and uranium dust (3 g.) were refluxed on a water-bath for 6 hours when a moderately vigorous reaction took place. The product was treated with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and the resulting yellow oil extracted with benzene, washed repeatedly with water, dried with anhydrous calcium chloride and fractionated; the fraction at 185-210° (redistilled at 198°-200°) was collected and identified as acetophenone, yield 1.2 g (6.3%).

Benzophenone from benzoyl chloride and benzene.—A mixture of benzoyl chloride (11 g.), benzene (15 g.) and uranium dust (3.5 g.) was heated on the sand-bath under reflux, till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased (8 hours). The mixture was then treated with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the benzene layer separated. It was washed with strong caustic soda solution repeatedly, and then with water, dried and fractionated at ordinary pressure. The pale yellow oil, distilling at 295°-310°, solidified on keeping for some hours and after crystallisation from alcohol melted at 46° and was identified as benzophenone, yield 2.3 g.

Ullmann's Reaction with Uranium Powder.

Diphenyl from bromobenzene.—Bromobenzene (10 g.) and uranium (8 g.) were refluxed at 170°-180° for 20 hours. The product was filtered and fractionated when after removal of bromobenzene at 155°-164° a very small amount of liquid distilled above 245° and solidified in the receiver. After crystallisation from a little alcohol it melted at 67° and was identified as diphenyl, yield 0.3 g.

Diphenyl from chlorobenzene.—Chlorobenzene (10 g.) and uranium (7 g.) were refluxed at 150°-160° for 20 hours and the product isolated as in the preceding case, yield 0.2 g.

Diphenyl from iodobenzene.—Iodobenzene (10 g.) and uranium (6 g.) were refluxed at 170°-190° for 20 hours and the product isolated as in the preceding cases, yield 0.4 g.

Diethylsuccinate from ethyl bromoacetate.—A mixture of ethyl bromoacetate (10 g.), ethyl acetate (10 g.) and uranium powder (3 g.) was refluxed at 110-120° for 15 hours and the product filtered, washed, dried and fractionated. The fraction at 200°-220° (redistilled at 216°-218°) was identified as diethylsuccinate, yield 1.4 g.

Adipic acid from β -iodopropionic acid.—When β -iodopropionic acid (10 g.) was heated with uranium (7 g.) first at 100° for 2

hours and then at 160°-165° for 8 hours, a little iodine was liberated. The product was extracted with hot water, filtered, and the filtrate on concentration gave *adipic acid*, m. p. 148°, yield 1.2 g.

Diphenyl ether from phenol and bromobenzene.—A mixture of pure anhydrous phenol (10 g.), bromobenzene (17 g.), uranium dust (3 g.) and freshly heated anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.8 g.) was refluxed at 180°-200° for 12 hours. The filtered product was distilled in steam and the distillate was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with dilute caustic soda and then with water, dried over calcium chloride and fractionated. The fraction at 240°-260° (redistilled at 253°-254°) was identified as diphenyl ether, yield 2.9 g.

Succinic acid from sodium chloroacetate and anhydrous sodium acetate.—A mixture of sodium chloroacetate (12 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (8 g.) and uranium (3 g.) when heated at 110°-120° for 3 hours gave very vigorous reaction. The product was extracted with water and ammonia added in slight excess to precipitate uranium hydroxide. The boiled and neutral filtrate was treated in the cold with neutral ferric chloride when ferric succinate was precipitated. This was filtered, washed with water thoroughly and decomposed by hydrogen sulphide. The filtrate from iron sulphide was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on complete evaporation gave 1.5 g. of *succinic acid*, m. p. 185°.

Zincke's Reaction with Uranium Powder.

Diphenylmethane and its higher homologues from benzyl chloride and benzene.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (30 g.), benzene (80 g.) dried over sodium, and uranium dust (4 g.) was slowly heated in an oil-bath up to 80° when a very vigorous reaction took place and torrents of hydrogen chloride were evolved. After the first vigorous reaction had subsided, the mixture was heated at 100-110° for 4 hours. The pink mixture was filtered from the metal and washed first with caustic soda and then with water. After dehydrating over anhydrous calcium chloride excess of benzene was removed on the water-bath and then fractionated. The fraction at 250°-280° was redistilled thrice and finally the portion distilling at 258°-261° was identified as diphenylmethane. It was a non-flourescent colourless liquid having an orange like smell and solidified on keeping in ice in thin radiating needles, m.p. 26°, [m.p. of pure diphenylmethane is 26.5° in literature and 28° by Smithe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1276) and gave on

oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate benzophenone, m. p. 47°. (Found: C, 92.34; H, 7.39. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{12}$: C, 92.85; H, 7.14 per cent).

The thick residual oil in the distilling flask was then fractionated under reduced pressure (14 mm.) and the first fraction (210°-260°) and the second (260-360)° were collected and then there was left a highly coloured and exceedingly viscous liquid which set to a hard, gum-like mass on cooling but softened and fused again on gentle warming. The first fraction had a violet fluorescence and on keeping overnight became semisolid which after removal of the oily portion by spreading on porous plate melted at 50-70°. By repeated crystallisation from alcohol, acetone and benzene in succession it was separated into two constituents; one, consisting of the more soluble fraction, m. p. 81-84° and the other m. p. 53-54°, b.p. 396°-400° at ordinary pressure identified to be *sym*triphenylethane. (Found: C, 92.75; H, 7.12. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{18}$: C, 93.02; H, 6.98 per cent.) and that melting at 81°-84° was found to be a mixture of *o*- and *p*-dibenzylbenzenes and as the quantity of the mixture was only 4.9 g. the complete separation of the two isomers was not possible. A small amount of sulphur-yellow hydrocarbon which on recrystallisation from alcohol melted 71° was also obtained (*cf.* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1278). Yield of dipenylmethane was 18.4 g. (40%), of *sym*triphenylethane was 3 g., of dibenzylbenzene was 4.9 g. and that of yellow hydrocarbon was 1 g. and about 5 g. of deep brown viscous residue were left in the distilling flask.

Phenetolyl-phenylmethane from phenetol and benzyl chloride.—A mixture of phenetol (20.4 g.), benzyl chloride (18.0 g.) and uranium dust (3.5 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath. A very vigorous reaction commenced at 70° and was completed by heating for 2 hours at 130° after the first vigorous reaction had subsided. The pink product having an intense violet fluorescence was extracted with benzene, filtered and the filtrate washed with caustic soda and water. The alkaline washings gave nothing on acidification and extraction with ether, showing that no demethylation had taken place during the course of the reaction as in the reactions with alkyl ethers of phenolic compounds in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$. The well washed benzene layer was dried over calcium chloride and fractionally distilled, the fractions above 300° being collected: (i) 305°-315°, (ii) 315°-345°, (iii) 345°-370°. The temperature then rose very quickly and (iv) a deep red liquid was left in the distilling flask (5 g.). The fraction (i) and (ii) were combined and redistilled, the fraction distilling at 330°-345°

(redistilled at 338°-341°) was identified as *p*-ethoxydiphenylmethane, yield 24.2 g. (80%). (Found: C, 84.64; H, 7.64. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O$: C, 84.92; H, 7.55 per cent). The residue left in the flask was an exceedingly thick liquid and nothing definite and crystalline could be obtained from it.

Anisoylphenylmethane from anisole and benzyl chloride.—A mixture of anisole (22 g.), benzyl chloride (21 g.), and uranium dust (3 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath up to 70° when a very vigorous reaction took place and after it had subsided the mixture was heated at 120°-130° for 3 hours. The pink reaction product having an intense violet fluorescence was extracted with hot benzene, filtered and the filtrate treated first with 5% caustic soda and then with water. The alkaline washing gave nothing after acidification and extraction with ether. The well washed benzene layer was separated, dried over calcium chloride and fractionated, the fractions distilling above 290° were collected: (i) 290°-315°, (ii) 315°-370°, and (iii) 370°-380°.

Fraction (i) (redistilled at 303°-305°) was identified to be anisoylphenylmethane (yield 17.4 g 52.9%) (cf. Rennie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1882, 41, 227). (Found: C, 84.41; H, 7.12. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O$: C, 84.84; H, 7.07 per cent) and the fraction distilling at 370°-380° was redistilled when most of it distilled at 376°-382° and was a very thick liquid with a very intense greenish blue fluorescence. (Found: C, 86.2; H, 7.12. $C_{21}H_{20}O$ requires C, 87.5; H, 6.94 per cent). It is probably dibenzylanisole (yield 6.9 g.).

Reformatsky's Reaction with Uranium Powder.

A mixture of acetophenone (12 g.), dried over metallic sodium, bromoacetic ester (17 g.), uranium dust (35 g.) and dry benzene (70 c. c.), dried over sodium, was gently warmed on the water-bath when a feeble reaction took place. After addition of a crystal of iodine the mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath at 120°-130° for 10 hours, by which time the mixture had become a pasty mass. After cooling, ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid was added to decompose the complex compound, the benzene layer separated, washed with dilute caustic soda and with water, dried over calcium chloride, and then fractionally distilled under highly reduced pressure. The fraction at 112°-130°/13 mm (redistilled at 118°-121°) was identified as phenylmethyl hydroxypropionic ester, yield 2.4 g.